

Bihula-Bishari Puja of Bhagalpur– Exploring Myth & Tradition

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Abstract: Since the dawn of human civilization, Mother Nature was perceived both in awe and loving appreciation, giving birth to a religion manifested in the worship of mother goddesses. Once widespread, this tradition found a lasting niche in India, particularly eastern India, where it still thrives. This article examines how myths, popular beliefs, and age-old customs interweave to sustain the living tradition of mother goddess worship in Bhagalpur, an ancient city in eastern India, highlighting the enduring relevance and specific practices in this region.

Keywords: Serpent Goddess, Manasa, Bishari, Bihula, Bhagalpur

Bhagalpur in the state of Bihar has a tradition of serpent goddess worship, which celebrates a religious practice four thousands year old. The worshipping of serpent Goddess Ma Manasa or Ma Bishari in local parlance, not only carries a tradition for generations, but it also encompasses a lore inter wind with the accompanied rituals which render it a unique flavor.

Religion in any form is a binding force to create a big society. It actually creates the society and sustains it. The Indian term for religion, Dharma, precisely defines its true meaning. The term dharma means, something which contains. What does it contain? It contains the whole society which is built around the core belief of that very religion. The humanity living within the society, their way of life, their culture,-reflecting their way of thinking, mode of worship et al are the reflections of the religion they believe in.

Around the world the manifestation of this phenomenon can be observed. A big chunk of humanity following a social order eventually forms a community having a single religion. The binding force of a religion depends on its universality. As the great thinker Harari observed- ‘...the majority of ancient religions were local and exclusive.’ Whether or not that religion includes other communities rests on its missionary nature and universal approach. The three great religions of the world namely Christianity, Islam and Buddhism have these qualities.

Well before the arrival of the major religions there was one universal religion spreading all over the world. That religion giving credence to nature sprang spontaneously at the dawn of civilization within the human societies across the world.

Thousands of year ago humans were in direct contact with nature. They saw both the benevolent and destructive aspects of it. Ancient people were in awe of Mother Nature, and they started to worship it as such. There were no idols to represent Mother Nature for worship in the beginning. Early humans saw her in trees, stones, mound of clay or in streams, hills and things like that; all part of Nature. The images of mother goddess came into being at a much latter period. But the aniconic form of worship still exists even today.

While the early humans recognized the existence of one supreme power called Nature, they still needed different gods and goddesses to fulfill their mundane desires. The oldest religion of the world thus spread all over the world. Different kinds of mother goddess which were found in different parts of the world still testify to that. There was a time when worshipping of Mother Goddess existed all over the world. In the present time only in India, particularly eastern India, one can find that tradition very much alive and kicking.

A researcher of Shaktism, June McDaniel in her book 'offering flowers, feeding skulls' pointed out –

'India has been worshipping goddesses continuously for thousands of years, and continues to do so today. If we accept the thousands of stone statues of women found at such ancient Indus Valley sites as Harappa, Mohenjo-Daro, and Lothal (these centers are usually dated from 2500 bce to 1500 bce) as goddess statues, as do many scholars, then goddess worship has been going on in India for at least four thousand years.'

Though in India mother goddess worship is not uncommon in different communities, only in Bengal it has a place of pride. No other community anywhere in India identify themselves with mother goddess worship more passionately than in Bengal. The Bengalis indeed are the only great race in the world to worship mother goddess in her varied forms. They took this tradition of Mother Goddess worship to the distant corners of their empire as they expanded it particularly during the reigns of Pala and Sena Dynasties.

Anga, one of the sixteen mahajanapadas of ancient India were governed by the different rulers of Gaur-Banga for many centuries. In fact it was a part of greater Bengal or Brihatbanga most of the time. It was but natural that the religiocultural environment of Anga resonated with that of Bengal. That historical fact may be the single most important reason that Mother Goddess of different kinds are still being worshipped and celebrated in present day Bhagalpur, the Anga of days of yore.

The tradition of worshipping mother goddess and Nagas (snakes) flows from the times of Harappan era. These two traditions were amalgamated in the worship of Ma Manasa. Snake Goddess images were also found in Chandraketugar, the 2500 years old center of Gangal/Gangar civilization.

Of all the Mother Goddess idols found in Pala era the most common were that of serpent goddess Ma Manasa or Janguli (a synonym for snake) tara of Bajrajana Buddhism.

Ma Manasa had a very distinct non-Vedic and outer Aryan origin. Having its origin in the harappan civilization Manasa puja was one of the greatest manifestations of the mass characteristic of Tantric religion. The unique feature of Ma Manasa was that, she imbibed the essence of most of the prominent matrikas or Mother Goddesses that the shaktas worship.

The infestation of snakes was a real problem in primitive world. Charming the Snakes was one of the main occupations of the lower strata of the society. The lowest rung of the Vedic cast system, the so called subalterns thus became the main worshipper of Ma Manasa, the snake goddess. The worshipping of the deity got acceptance in the higher cast brahminical society only in the latter years.

The tradition of the worshipping of the Snake Goddess in Bhagalpur (modern name of Anga) was very old. The archeological finds comprising small terracotta figurines with snake motifs excavated from sites in and around Bhagalpur placed the date to the Harappan era.

Champanagar (or Champa, the old capital of Anga), an area within the Nathnagar block of Bhagalpur held a temple dedicated to Ma Manasa. The place of worship was said to be very old, though the building was of recent origin. If the words of a Local researcher to be believed there was a feature that still exist just behind the altar that bears the deity, which resembles twin snake object found among the harappan artifacts. Legend had it that Chand sadagar, the wealthy merchant of Champa paid a visit to this temple.

The names of Chand sadagar, his son Lakhinder and daughter in law Behula with their tale of woes were the integral part of the rituals that accompany the worshipping of Ma Manasa.

Each year the ceremony started with the placing of kalas or pitcher on the month of 'Ashad' (Mid July) on the seventh day of the moon. Exactly one month later when the sun entered the zodiac sign Leo, the idol of Ma Manasa was placed on the altar for worship. Hundreds of idols of Ma Manasa were worshiped throughout Bhagalpur and its adjacent areas in those days.

Champanagar stands at the confluence of the river Ganga and a smaller but important river Champa sharing the same name as the city. It was said that Chand sadagar's merchant ships sailed through the champa river carrying merchandises that included silk, spices and other valuable items. Recent archeological find of an ancient harbor at the confluence of the two rivers may induce one to believe that.

Many places in Jataka the opulence of Champa and its wealthy marchants were mentioned. The place was also known for the production of silk and its export to many places in and out of the country. Modern Champanagar is still the source of world renowned Bhagalpuri silk.

The mention of snake Goddess as Ma Manasa first appeared in epic poems (Manasamangal-Kavya), written in praise of the mother goddess and describing the establishment of her worship by a thirteenth century Bengali poet kana Haridatta during the reign of the Palas.

The story line of all the manasa kavyas contains the tale of Chand sadagar, a worshiper of Shiva and his antagonisms with Ma Manasa. Chand refused to worship Manasa at first, but agreed to do so after many trials and tribulations. In the process all his sons died due to the wrath of Manasa. When his seventh son Lakhinder was born and grew up to be married to Behula, a beautiful lady from Ujani, he too was put to death on the wedding night by means of a snake bite as arranged by Manasa. Behula then took with her the lifeless body of her husband on a raft made out of plantain trunks and sailed away to heaven through the Champa river. She managed to revive her husband eventually by the grace of Ma Manasa but with a condition that her father in law Chand sadagar had to pay obeisance to her.

These key events from the Manasa mangal kavyas were incorporated within the rituals which accompany Manasa or Bishari puja in Bhagalpur still today. This story itself gave rise to a beautiful local art called Manjusha which was unique to Bhagalpur. The art using the colors green, orange and yellow depicts the events from the saga.

Interestingly according to local belief all the characters and places mentioned in the manasamangal kavya can be found in and around Bhagalpur. But how the story set in Bengal intermingled with the religious ceremony performed at Bhagalpur, a town in Bihar?! As I mentioned before, this land was very much a part of brihat-banga or Greater Bengal in ancient times. It was suggested by noted historian Denesh Chandra Sen that the songs sung in Hindi on the occasion of Bishari puja were greatly influenced by the first mangal kavya written by poet Kana Haridutta at a time when palas ruled supreme here. This was mentioned by Dinesh Chandra Sen in the first part of his epitome 'Brihatbanga'.

It should be noted too that in pre Christian era Bengal had a thriving trading society with trade links with ancient civilizations. It's a plausible conjecture put forward by Dr. Tamal Dasgupta. Chand sadagar was a wealthy merchant whose ships sailed to distant lands with merchandises. It was very likely he had his base in the thriving trading center at champanagar too.

Although the topology of Bengal appeared vividly in Manasamangal kavya, the heritage of Chand sadagar was claimed by many in various places in eastern India. The Bihula-Manasa story, which was an integral part of the snake goddess worship also found its place in local imagination. Thus we have abode of Chand sadagar and bihula in places like Bardhaman in west Bengal, Bhagalpur in Bihar and chayagaon in Kamrup district of Assam. Mahasthangarh in Bogura district of north Bengal (now in Bangladesh) boasts of the bridal chamber of Behula and Lakhinder so do the karnagarh in Bhagalpur. Interestingly all these places are situated near important river systems which must have served as trading routes. Damodar in Bardhaman, Korotoya in Bogura, Brahmaputra in Assam and Ganges and Champa River in Bhagalpur. Were they interlinked? Most likely they were.

When history was too old and obscured with the haze of time it appeared as myths and legends. But it still held the grain of truth, like the pearl concealing the grain of sand within it. The truth concerning the history should better be left to the experts of the field, the historians, as we were not here to chase a fading trail of history. Instead we should appreciate the exuberance of an ancient religious practice steeped in local tradition which is still vibrant and alive in Bhagalpur.

References

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